

LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROVERBS WITH THE SUBJECT “SEASON”

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This article talks about the meaning of the concept of seasons in English, its similarities and differences with other languages in the lexical field. Also, an opinion was expressed about the ethnographic information about the season through linguistic and cultural analysis.

Weather proverbs, folk sayings, are observed in every society to forecast atmospheric conditions. In English and Arabic, weather proverbs are presented as a collection of opinions, philosophies and thoughts of people towards climatic conditions. Yet, they are often uttered in fixed forms (words, expressions, phrases and sentences); that is, they enjoy miscellaneous linguistic (syntactic, lexical and semantic) characteristics and being realized in different senses when located in various settings.

The term “proverbs” sets up an essential part of every society and language. They exist to help people to attain various jobs as they deliver a plenty of senses and purposes linked to people's ideologies, opinions, beliefs, performances, circumstances and social patterns of life. That is, proverbs constitute a vital part of the people's folklore, and are often made use of whenever the numerous situations they attend recur. In fact, they are utterances that reflect ethics, principles and social practices of everyday life of common people. Thus, they unveil the manner

people think about the world, and subsequently exhibit abundant effect on people's ways and manners of living.

They are depicted in the situation of ordinary communication achieving the same functions, evidently, as other folk and everyday utterances.

The original form of *summer* remains a matter of dispute. From Old English we have *sumor*, but, outside English this word also existed with the suffix *-ar*. All modern dictionaries identify the root (*sum-*) with Sanskrit *sáma* “half-year; year (!); season.” Despite the fact that this root is familiar from Latin *semi-* “half-,” questions remain. We are supposed to conclude that the year was divided not into three or four seasons but into two (rainy and dry? warm and cold?), that the name of the warm season became synonymous with “season as such, season in general,” and that those who used the word in question reckoned years by summers (like the Slavs). None of it is improbable. The trouble lies elsewhere. Many languages have words with the root *sam-* ~ *sem-* “half,” but the people among whom *sáma* was current lived on the Indian peninsula. So it is unclear why the Germanic speakers, who never inhabited those regions and had limited contacts with its population, adopted their word for “summer” and used it instead of some other Indo-European name of the season or of a more appropriate neologism. Their year was not divided into two seasons, as happens in south Asia. Despite the consensus on the etymology of *summer*, all is not clear, and this is the reason it might be useful to cite another etymology lost in the jungle of conjectures and hypotheses.

Regardless of the proverbs and sayings of which people we are considering, it can be said with confidence that this genre of folklore is undoubtedly part of the world heritage. Proverbs and

sayings determine the mentality and are passed down from generation to generation in oral and written form, developing along with the development of mankind.

Nevertheless, despite some similarities in the paremias of the studied languages (mutual calques, borrowings from classical languages, biblical texts), Uzbek and English proverbs developed under different historical circumstances, reflecting the socio-economic structure and development conditions, which are not identical in these cultures. The nature of the use of proverbs also differs, their prevalence in various strata of society, the prestige of experts on proverbs, etc.

The linguistic analysis of English and Uzbek season proverbs comes up with the finding that Weather proverbs in both English and Uzbek are essentially those proverbs that involve weather vocabulary and expressions utilized to reflect climatic state. The intent and function of a weather proverb in both English and Uzbek languages are noticeably reflected through their structural behaviors. The four types of sentences (simple, compound, complex and compound-complex) are exploited in both languages to express various sorts of meaning. Further, Simple sentential weather proverbs (denoting single ideas) in English are primarily expressed by the structure pattern in which the subject is followed by a verb, whereas in Uzbek, both nominal and verbal sentences are exploited to express single ideas associated with climate state.

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